

Knowledge, Attitudes and Practices of Irish Dietitians on Nutritional Management Approaches for Infantile Regurgitation and Reflux

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Background: Infantile regurgitation and reflux are common, self-limiting conditions in early infancy but frequently prompt caregiver concern and healthcare-seeking behaviour. Although Foods for Special Medical Purposes (FSMPs) are regulated for use under medical supervision, limited evidence exists on how Irish dietitians support conservative management and navigate FSMP-related decision-making, particularly in relation to anti-reflux formulas (ARFs).

Aim & objectives: To examine Irish dietitians' knowledge, attitudes, and practices regarding the dietary management of infantile regurgitation and reflux, particularly ARF use.

Research Design: A 30-item cross-sectional online survey was distributed to registered dietitians practicing in Ireland to assess knowledge, attitudes, and practices related to infantile regurgitation and reflux. Data were analysed using descriptive statistics, Chi-square tests, and Spearman's correlation in SPSS, with statistical significance set at $p < 0.05$.

Results: Twenty-seven dietitians completed the survey. Conservative strategies were widely implemented to manage infantile regurgitation, particularly feeding-technique optimisation (96.4% for reflux; 85.7% for regurgitation) and parental reassurance (85% for both conditions). Recommendation of ARFs was infrequent: 62% of dietitians reported rarely or never recommending ARFs for reflux, and 79.3% for regurgitation. Unsupervised caregiver-initiated ARFs occurred in 33.3% and 27.8% of reflux and regurgitation cases. Confidence in dietary management of both conditions without use of ARFs was significantly associated with clinical exposure of regurgitation ($p < 0.001$) and reflux ($p = 0.012$).

Conclusion: This study identifies a disconnect between regulatory requirements mandating the use of ARFs under medical supervision, professional recommendations, and caregiver-initiated use of ARFs. Practical training for dietitians and clearer communication with caregivers is needed to ensure ARF is used safely and according to evidence.